

Reactions of Some Benzofuran Derivatives with Amides, Nitriles and Hydrazines

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When 6-acetoacetyl-5-methoxy-(1b) and 5-acetoacetyl-6-methoxy-2,3-diphenylbenzofuran (2b) were treated with cyanoacetamide, the corresponding nicotinonitriles were obtained.

Compounds 1b and 2b reacted with ethyl cyanoacetate in presence of ammonium acetate to give the benzofuranyl-pyrone derivatives while when the reactions were carried out in presence of diethylamine led to the formation of furochromones.

Hydrazine hydrate, phenylhydrazine and semicarbazide hydrochloride reacted with 1b and 2b with the formation of the corresponding pyrazoles.

The corresponding isoxazole derivatives were formed by the reaction of 1b and 2b with hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

It is well known that pyridine, pyrazole, pyrone, isoxazole and benzofuran derivatives showed a marked biological activity¹⁻⁵. Thus, the present investigation deals with combination of pyridine, pyrone, pyrazole and isoxazole nuclei with benzofuran ring in order to obtain new compounds of potential biological activity.

Both compounds 6-acetyl-5-methoxy- (1a) and 5-acetyl-6-methoxy-2, 3-diphenylbenzofuran (2a)⁶ undergo Claisen condensation with ethyl acetate in presence of sodium metal to give 6-acetoacetyl-5-methoxy- (1b) and 5-acetoacetyl-6-methoxy-2, 3-diphenylbenzofuran (2b), respectively. The i.r. spectra of compounds 1b and 2b showed bands at 1622 and 1618 cm⁻¹ for tautomeric keto-enol forms⁷.

The m.s. of compound 1b exhibited a molecular ion M⁺ at m/e 384 (40%), the major fragmentation was the elimination of one mole of acetone yielding ion a as base peak at m/e 326 (100%), due to the ortho effect of functional groups attached to benzene ring of benzofuran molecule⁸. The ion a decomposed further by expulsion of carbon monoxide, the reasonable structure for this ion a can be illustrated by the following mechanism :

The p.m.r spectrum of compound 1b showed the singlets at δ 2.20 (3H, CH₃), 3.88 (3H, OCH₃), 7.00 (1H, C-4), 8.17 (1H, C-7) and 6.62 (1H, olefinic), also 10 aromatic protons appeared as multiplets at δ 7.30-7.56. The spectrum of compound 2b revealed the signals $\alpha + \delta$ 2.10 s(3H, CH₃), 3.96 s(3H, OCH₃) 7.06 s(1H, C-4), 7.96 s(1H, C-7), 6.40 s(1H olefinic) and 7.40-7.60 m(10H, aromatic).

When compounds 1b and 2b were treated with cyanoacetamide in presence of ammonium acetate, led to the formation of 4-(2',3'-diphenyl-5'-methoxy-6'-benzofuranyl)- (3) and 4-(2',3'-diphenyl-6'-methoxy-5'-benzofuranyl)-1, 2-dihydro-2-oxo-6-methylnicotinonitrile (4).

The ir spectra of compounds 3 and 4 revealed the presence of >C=O group at 1630 and 1625 cm⁻¹ (tautomeric pyridone), -C≡N group at 2230 and 2225 cm⁻¹ and NH group at 3150 and 3160 characteristic for -NH stretching frequency in substituted 2-pyridone^{9,10}. The m.s. of compound 3 showed a molecular ion M⁺ at m/e 432. The p.m.r. spectra of compounds 3 and 4 were in agreement with the assigned structures. The spectrum for compound 3 showed signals at δ 2.68 s(3H, CH₃), 3.97 s(3H, OCH₃), 7.15 s(1H, C'-4), 7.85 s(1H, C'-7), 7.07 s(1H, C-5) and 7.30-7.70 m(10H, aromatic). Compound 4 revealed the singlets at δ 2.51 (3H, CH₃), 4.05 (3H, OCH₃), 7.25 (1H, C'-4), 7.61 (1H, C'-7) and 7.12 (1H, C-5), also 10 aromatic protons appeared as multiplets at δ 7.30-7.55.

The behaviour of the diketones 1b and 2b with ethylcyanoacetate was also investigated. When the reaction was carried out in presence of ammonium acetate, 4-(2', 3'-diphenyl-5'-methoxy-6'-benzofuranyl)- (5) and 4-(2', 3'-diphenyl-6'-methoxy-5'-benzofuranyl)-3-cyano-6-methyl-pyran-2-one (6) were obtained.

On the other hand, when the above reaction was carried out in presence of diethylamine or piperidine as a catalyst, gave 2,3-diphenyl-7-methyl-8H-furo [2, 3-g] [1] benzopyran-8-one¹¹ (7) and 2,3-diphenyl-7-methyl-5H-furo [3, 2-g] [1] benzopyran-5-one¹¹ (8) (m.p. and mixed m. p. with an authentic sample gave no depression). The furochromones 7 and 8 were also yielded by reflux 1b and 2b with diethylamine or piperidine in ethanol, probably via demethylation followed by cyclodehydration¹⁸.

The ir spectra of compounds 5 and 6 showed bands at 1750 and 1745 cm^{-1} characteristic for α, β -unsaturated- δ -lactone¹⁴. The bands at 2220 and 2235 cm^{-1} were due to $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ group.

The p.m.r spectrum of compound 7 have not been reported. The spectrum showed the singlets at δ 7.32 (1H, C-4), 6.15 (1H, C-6), 8.28 (1H, C-9) and 2.37 (3H, CH_3), also 10 aromatic protons appeared as multiplets at δ 7.38-7.65. The m.s. of compound 7 showed a molecular ion M^+ at m/e 352 as base peak.

The present investigation described also the synthesis of 4-(2',3'-5'-methoxy-6'-benzofuranyl)- (9) and 4-(2',3'-diphenyl-6'-methoxy-5'-benzofuranyl)-3-cyano-6-methyl-2-pyranoimide (10), by the reaction of compounds 1b and 2b with malononitrile in presence of ammonium acetate, respectively.

The infra-red spectra of compounds 9 and 10 showed the absence of $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group and revealed bands at 1630 and 1625 cm^{-1} due to $-\text{C}=\text{N}$ group, bands at 2230 and 2225 cm^{-1} characteristic for $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ group.

The diketones 1b and 2b reacted with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol or in acetic acid to yield 3-(2', 3'-diphenyl-5'-methoxy-6'-benzofuranyl)- (11a) and 3-(2', 3'-diphenyl-6'-methoxy-5'-benzofuranyl)-5-methylpyrazole (12a), respectively.

N. phenylpyrazoles 11b and 12b were formed by the reaction of 1b and 2b with phenyl hydrazine. The ir spectra of compounds 11a, 11b, 12a and 12b showed bands at 1620-1630 cm^{-1} responsible for $-\text{C}=\text{N}$ group.

The reaction of compounds 1b and 2b with semicarbazide hydrochloride led to the formation of the corresponding pyrazoles 11c and 12c, respectively.

a, R = H b, R = C_6H_5 c, R = CONH_2

Compounds 3-(2', 3'-diphenyl-5'-methoxy-6'-benzofuranyl)- (13) and 3-(2', 3'-diphenyl-6'-methoxy-5'-benzofuranyl)-5-methylisoxazole were furnished by the reaction of 1b and 2b with hydroxylamine hydrochloride, respectively.

Experimental

Melting points were not corrected. PMR spectra were obtained at 60 MHz in CDCl_3 with TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were run at 70 eV. The infra-red spectra were carried out in potassium bromide on a Unicam Infra-red Spectrophotometer Model SP 2000.

Preparation of 6-acetoacetyl-5-methoxy-2, 3-diphenylbenzofuran (1b) :

A solution of 4g of 1a in 50 ml of ethyl acetate was slowly added to 4g of powdered sodium metal. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 hrs and then left to

cool. After working up, the aqueous layer was acidified with acetic acid and the solid that separated was crystallized from ethanol to give compound 1b as yellow needles. m.p. 158°; yield 80%. *Analysis*: for $C_{28}H_{20}O_4$ (384); Calcd. C 78.13, H 5.21; Found C 78.23, H 5.45.

5-Acetoacetyl-6-methoxy-2, 3-diphenylbenzofuran (2b):

It was prepared from 4g of 2a in 50 ml of ethyl acetate and 4g of powdered sodium as in case of 1b. Compound 2b was obtained as yellow needles from ethanol, m.p. 153-155°; yield 85%. *Analysis*: for $C_{28}H_{20}O_4$ (384); Calcd. C 78.13, H 5.21; Found C 78.10, H 5.41.

4 - (2', 3'-Diphenyl-5'-methoxy-6'-benzofuranyl)-1,2-dihydro-2-oxo-6-methylnicotinitrile (3) :

A mixture of 1b (1g), cyanoacetamide (1g) and ammonium acetate (2g) in 20 ml of acetic acid was refluxed for one hr, then left to cool. The solid that separated was crystallized from ethanol to give 3 as yellow crystals, m.p. 265°; yield 75%. *Analysis*: for $C_{28}H_{20}N_2O_3$ (432); Calcd. C 77.78, H 4.63, N 6.48; Found C 77.49, H 4.35, N 6.56%.

4-(2', 3'-Diphenyl 6'-methoxy-5'-benzofuranyl)-1, 2-dihydro-2-oxo-6-methylnicotinonitrile (4) :

In a similar manner as in 3, 1g of 2b, 1g of cyanoacetamide and 2g of ammonium acetate in 20 ml of acetic acid gave 4 as yellow crystals from ethanol, m.p. 291°; yield 80%. *Analysis*: for $C_{28}H_{20}N_2O_3$ (432); Calcd. C 77.78, H 4.63, N 6.48; Found C 77.81, H 4.89, N 6.67%.

4-(2',3'-Diphenyl-5'-methoxy-6'-benzofuranyl)-3-cyano-6-methyl-pyran-2-one (5) :

A mixture of 1b (1g), ethyl cyanoacetate (1 ml) and ammonium acetate (2g) in 20 ml of acetic acid was refluxed for 3 hrs, then left to cool. The solid so obtained was crystallized from ethanol to give compound 5 as cream fibers, m.p. 105°; yield 80%. *Analysis* for $C_{28}H_{19}NO_4$ (433); Calcd. C 77.60, H 4.39, N 3.23; Found C 77.83, H 4.59, N 3.42%.

4-(2', 3' -Diphenyl- 6' -methoxy-5'-benzofuranyl)-3-cyano-6-methyl-pyran-2-one :

A mixture of 2b (1g), ethyl cyanoacetate (1 ml) and ammonium acetate (2g) in 20 ml of acetic acid gave 75% of 6 as cream needles from ethanol, m.p. 142°. *Analysis* for $C_{28}H_{19}NO_4$ (433); Calcd. C 77.60, H 4.39, N 3.23, Found C 77.65, H 4.42, N 3.45%.

2,3-Diphenyl-7-methyl 8H-furo [2,3-g] [1] benzopyran-8-one (7) :

To a mixture of 1b (1g) and ethyl cyanoacetate in 50 ml of ethanol diethylamine (1 ml), (or piperidine) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs. then left to cool. The solid that separated was crystallized from ethanol to give compound 7 as white crystals, m.p. 213°; yield 90%. (m.p. and mixed m.p. with the known compound ¹¹ gave no depression).

2,3-Diphenyl-7-methyl-5H-furo[3, 2-g][1] benzopyran-5-one (8) :

As in case of 7 1g of 2b gave compound 8 as white crystals m.p. 204°; yield 80%, (m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample¹² gave no depression).

4-(2',3'-Diphenyl-5'-methoxy-6'-benzofuranyl)-3-cyano-6-methyl-2-pyranoimide (9) :

A mixture of 1b (1g), malononitrile (1g) and ammonium acetate (2g) in 20 ml of acetic acid was refluxed for 3 hrs, then left to cool. The solid so obtained was crystallized from ethanol to give 9 as white crystals, m.p. 180°; yield 60%. *Analysis* for $C_{28}H_{20}N_2O_3$ (432); Calcd. C 77.78, H 4.63, N 6.48; Found C 77.97, H 4.69, N 6.64%.

4-(2',3'-Diphenyl-6-methoxy-5'-benzofuranyl)-3-cyano-6-methyl-2-pyranoimide (10) :

In a similar manner as in case of 9 2b(1g), malononitrile (1g) and ammonium acetate (2g) in 20 ml of acetic acid gave 55% of 10 as cream crystals from ethanol, m.p. 170°. *Analysis* for $C_{28}H_{20}N_2O_3$ (432); Calcd. C 77.78, H 4.63, N 6.48; Found C 77.62, H 4.34, N 6.72%.

Reaction of 1b and 2b with hydrazine hydrate or phenyl hydrazine :

A mixture of 1g of 1b or 2b and 0.5 ml of hydrazine hydrate (99%) or phenylhydrazine in 50 ml of ethanol or 20 ml of acetic acid was refluxed for 5 hrs, then concentrated to about 10 ml, diluted with water and left to cool, and the solid so obtained was crystallized from ethanol.

The pyrazole 11a was obtained as colourless crystals, m.p. 222°; yield 75%. *Analysis* for $C_{28}H_{20}N_2O_2$ (380); Calcd. C 78.95, H 5.26, N 7.37; Found C 78.65, H 5.55, N 7.56%.

P.M.R. (TFA) δ 2.60 s (3H, CH₃), 4.07 s (3H, OCH₃), 7.17 s (1H, C'-4), 7.95 s (1H, C'-7), 6.87 s (1H, C-4) and 7.30-7.60 m (10H, aromatic). Mol. Wt. M⁺ m/e 380.

12a was formed in 75% yield as cream crystals, m.p. 190°. *Analysis* for $C_{28}H_{20}N_2O_2$ (380); Calcd. C 78.95, H 5.26, N 7.37; Found C 78.80, H 5.20, N 7.33%.

P.M.R. δ 3.94 s (3H, OCH₃), 2.27 s (3H, CH₃), 7.20 s (1H, C'-4), 7.63 s (1H, C'-7) 7.08 s (1H, C-4) and 7.30-7.55 m (10H, aromatic).

The compound 11b was formed as cream crystals, m.p. 218°; yield 70% *Analysis* for $C_{28}H_{20}N_2O_2$ (456) Calcd. C 81.58, H 5.26, N 6.14; Found C 81.74, H 5.05, N 5.80%.

P.M.R. δ 2.43 s (3H, CH₃), 3.33 s (3H, OCH₃), 6.36 (1H, C'-4), 6.83s s (1H, C'-7), 7.40 s (1H, C-4) and 7.30-7.60 m (15H, aromatic). Mol. Wt. M⁺ m/e 456.

N phenylpyrazole 12b was furnished as cream crystals, m.p. 116°; yield 60%. *Analysis* for $C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_3$ (456): Calcd. C 81.58, H 5.26, N 6.14: Found C 81.32, H 5.41, N 6.27%.

P.M.R. δ 2.36 s(3H, CH_3), 3.40 s(3H, OCH_3), 6.25 s(1H, C'-4), 6.95 s(1H, C'-7), 7.30 s(1H, C-4) and 7.20-7.60 m(15H, aromatic).

Preparation of pyrazoles 11c and 12c :

A solution of 0.004 mole of 1b or 2b in least amount of ethanol was added to a solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride in least amount of water. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs, then cooled, and the solid that separated was crystallized from ethanol.

The pyrazole 11c was obtained as colourless crystals, m. p. 220°; yield 80%. *Analysis* for $C_{26}H_{21}N_3O_3$ (423): Calcd, C 73.76, H 4.96, N 9.93: Found C 73.53, H 5.33, N 9.99%.

12c was formed as colourless crystals, m.p. 265°; yield 78%. *Analysis* for $C_{26}H_{21}N_3O_3$ (423): Calcd. C 73.76, H 4.96, N 9.93: Found C 73.49, H 4.81, N 9.84%.

3-(2', 3'-Diphenyl-5'-methoxy-6'-benzofuranyl)-5-methylisoxazole (13) :

A solution of 0.5g of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and 0.2g of sodium acetate in least amount of water was added to a suspension of 1.9g of 1b in 50 ml of ethanol. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 hrs. On cooling and addition of water, a solid separated, was crystallized from ethanol to give 13 as colourless crystals m.p. 200°; yield 80%. *Analysis* for $C_{25}H_{19}NO_3$ (381): Calcd C 78.74, H 4.99, N 3.67: Found C 78.66, H 5.10, N 3.82%.

P.M.R. δ 2.38 s(3H, CH_3), 3.93 s(3H, OCH_3), 7.00 s(1H, C'-4), 8.18 s(1H, C'-7), 6.72 s(1H, C-4) and 7.40-7.60 m(10H, aromatic).

3-(2', 3' - Diphenyl-6'-methoxy-5'-benzofuranyl)-5-methylpyrazole (14) :

In similar manner as in case of 13, 2b (1.9g) gave 14 as colourless crystals, m.p. 163°; yield 80%. *Analysis* for $C_{25}H_{19}NO_3$ (381): Calcd. C 78.74, H 4.99, N 3.76: Found C 78.54, H 5.22, N 3.82%.

P.M.R. δ 2.33 s(3H, CH_3), 4.00 s(3H, OCH_3), 7.02 s(C'-4, 1H), 8.04 s(1H, C'-7), 6.65 s(1H, C-4) and 7.30-7.65 m(10H, aromatic).

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